

Causes Factor and Impact of Work-School Conflict at Work and Health: Study of College Student-Employee

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Abstract:- The era that is increasingly developing requires companies to have human resources with skills according to the needs of developing the company. Individuals are also required to improve their quality so individuals can compete in the world of work and develop their careers. It is not uncommon for students to decide to become employees in an effort to improve their self-quality. However, this can lead to conflict because individuals have to balance the fulfillment of responsibilities between the roles of student and employee so that later it can interfere with one of the roles. This is called a work-school conflict. Thus, this research was conducted to describe the causes factors, as well as the impact at work and health regarding the work-school conflict in college student-employees. In data processing, this study uses a systematic review method with narrative techniques. This study used 25 selected journals for review. Based on the results of the review, the causes factors are grouped into three, namely those originating from individuals, roles at school, and roles at work. In addition, this study also found an impact on work-school conflict related to work and health. This research is expected to provide benefits related to the understanding that college student-employees as individuals and companies are involved in avoiding or reducing the possibility of work-school conflict occurring.

Keywords:- *Work-School Conflict, College Student-Employee, Causes Factor, Impact.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of an increasingly advanced era certainly has a good impact on human life. However, the progress of this era brings its own challenges, especially now that humans live in the digital era. As quoted from the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (2019), that the job market has experienced development as a result of technological changes, but there are still many countries that are lagging behind in terms of the skills of their employees needed in the world of work in today's digital era. Meanwhile, research conducted by Price Waterhouse Coopers (2022) states that currently, human resources are the most

important tool for company development. Bohle, Chambel, Medina, and Cunha (2018) also said that today's global competition is increasingly high. According to data from the International Labor Organization (The World Bank, 2022), the world unemployment rate in 2021 will reach 6.2%, this figure is in second place with a period of 1991-2021, and the last occurred in 2003. International Labor Organization (2022) also expressed concern regarding youth unemployment rates in many countries.

This shows that individuals are required to improve their quality in career development to be able to compete in the job market, so individuals can adapt to the times and not be left behind. Savickas (2002) through his theory regarding the stages of career development argues that during the transition from school to work, individuals must take actions that can make the desired career a reality. This is usually done by developing the skills needed by the individual in the desired job by continuing school, training, or apprenticeship. Also at this stage, the individual begins to try a particular job, so that the individual can develop a career through skills, to get a job according to individual desires. In fact, it is not uncommon for organizations to invest in employees to obtain advanced degrees (Wyland, Lester, Mone, and Winkel, 2013). Because as already described, the quality of employees is not only related to individual career development but also related to the development of the company.

The demand to adapt and develop means that it is not uncommon for students to work for their career development. The National Center for Education Statistics (2022) explains that many undergraduate students aged 16-64 carry out multiple roles as employees at the same time when undergraduate students attend school. Summarizing data for 2015 and 2020 found that in 2020 as many as 40% of undergraduate students carried out the role as full-time employees, and 74% as part-time employees, where this number is lower than in 2015 (National Center for Education Statistics, 2022). In addition, The National Center for Education Statistics describes the number of each student working based on race/ethnicity, namely White students (42% full-time, 78% part-time), Black students (33% full-time, 70% part-time), Hispanic students (43% full-time, 74% part-time),

Asian students (28% full-time, 56% part-time), American Indian/Alaska Native (21% full-time), and students with two or more races (40% full-time).

Students are defined as a group in society who have young human characteristics and intellectual candidates, and have a role as agents who bring about changes in a logical and realistic order of life, which is accepted by society (Sejati & Prihastuti, 2012). The reason students also carry out the role of employees is to get paid to meet their daily needs, cover tuition fees (Baldwin, Wilkinson, & Barkley, 2000), earn extra money for fun, and improve personal and social skills (Verulava & Jorbenadze, 2022). However, research revealed by Mills, Lingard, and Wakefield (2007), that the reason students work in the first place is because it has a beneficial impact on long-term careers and undergraduate studies in students. The career itself is defined by Super (1980) as referring to the combination and sequence of roles performed by an individual during a lifetime. From the definitions of students and careers that have been described, students who work are carrying out multiple roles, namely the roles of students and employees.

According to Super (1980), playing several roles in life will be associated with success and satisfaction, but when individuals play several roles simultaneously during the same life stage, it will lead to role conflict, individuals will have difficulty being fair in giving their commitment to the roles carried out. This is also what Rigio (2013) said, that expectations in one role can interfere with expectations in other roles which causes role conflict. Thus, role conflict may also be experienced by students who are also employees in the educational process at tertiary institutions. This role conflict in working students is called work-school conflict.

Work-school conflict refers to the extent to which work demands and responsibilities can interfere with an employee's ability to fulfill demands and responsibilities at school (Andrade, 2018). This understanding shows that work-school conflict is more associated with an impact on the role of a student, but work-school conflict involves two roles, which means it also has the potential to have an impact on the role of an employee. This was revealed by Mills, Lingard, and Wakefield (2007) that work-school conflict is a phenomenon that involves two directions, how individual responsibility for roles in work will interfere with individual responsibility for roles in school, and how individual responsibility for roles in school will interfere with individual responsibility to the role in the job.

Work-school conflict itself can be caused by several factors, such as high working hours, high job demand, and low job control (Butler, 2007). Work-school conflict can affect individuals both in terms of physical and mental health as well as their performance in carrying out their roles as employees. Research has found that working students feel sleep deprived, and their limited time and job roles make working students less willing to learn more about the company where they work (Phakdi, 2013). Another study by Brunel and Grima (2010) found that work-school conflict affects stress, and it was found that high stress can also affect

turnover intention due to work-school conflict experienced. Therefore, it is feared that the work-school conflict experienced by college students-employees will have a further impact that can be detrimental to the organization. Therefore, a study was conducted to systematically analyze the antecedents, job and health outcomes of work-school conflict among working students. This research is expected to provide understanding to working students and companies related to the causes and impact of work-school conflict at work and health on working students. Thus, working students are expected to be able to balance the multiple roles being carried out, which in the end will get successful career development with satisfaction. Meanwhile, companies can produce human resources that will support the development of the company. In addition, it is hoped that companies will gain insight regarding younger employees, where this will represent the workforce in the future (Park & Sprung, 2015).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mark and Frone (1998) stated that work-school conflict refers to the extent to which work can interfere with an individual's ability to meet the demands and responsibilities at school. The model of work-school conflict was developed using the theory of work-family conflict, both of which involve two roles in life, if the work-family conflict involves roles in work and roles in the family, while work-school conflict involves roles in work and roles within schools (Mark & Frone, 1998). Even though the definition directs more impact on roles in college, work-school conflict also has the potential to become a two-way concept like work-family conflict (Laughman, Boyd, & Rusbasan, 2016). This shows that work-school conflict allows the role of an employee to interfere with the role of a student, whereas the role of a student can interfere with the role of an employee. Thus, individuals who experience work-school conflict have the potential to experience a negative impact on their roles as employees and as students.

Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) revealed that there are three main forms of conflict between roles, namely time-based conflict, strain-based conflict, and behavior-based conflict. Time-based conflict is a conflict that occurs because the time pressure in one role does not match the demands in another role, thus the time spent involved in one role tends not to be devoted to engaging in another role. Strain-based conflict occurs when one role creates a strain that makes it difficult for individuals to fulfill the demands of other roles. Meanwhile, behavior-based conflict is a conflict that occurs when individuals cannot adjust their behavior to meet expectations in two different roles, the behavior patterns of one role may tend to be inconsistent with the expectations of behavior patterns in other roles.

According to Markel and Frone (1998), there are three predictors of work-study conflict, namely working time, job dissatisfaction, and workload. Owen, Kavanagh, & Dollard (2017) added that other factors that influence work-study conflict are support, both social, family, campus and work. The work-school conflict that is experienced will have an impact on both the health and performance of college student-

employees in the company. Research on a literature study conducted by Choo, Kan and Cho (2021) found that work-school conflict can cause work stress, decrease job satisfaction, and affect performance. Another study found that college-student employees experience sleep deprivation as a result of the difficulty in carrying out their roles as employees and students, then sleep deprivation affects student health such as causing irritation, bad temper, decreased concentration, headache, fatigue, deterioration, unpleasant feelings, chronic fatigue syndrome, memory impairment, nervous system disorder, stress, increased pressure, fainting, and lost productivity (Verulava & Jorbenadze, 2022). Based on this explanation, the impact of work-school conflict experiences on college students-employees is known to be detrimental to employees as individuals and further to the company where individuals work. An understanding of work-school conflict is important for both parties to be able to control and determine steps to resolve the conflict so that it does not have an impact that will be detrimental to both.

III. METHOD

A. Procedures

This research was conducted to find the causes and impacts of work-school conflict at work and health on working students, by examining the literature collected from various sources, including American Psychological Association, Emerald, Google Scholar, SAGE Publication, Elsevier, Springer, Wiley, Taylor & Francis Online, Dynasty Publishers, Psymphatic, and GARUDA Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology. In this study, the data processing used a systematic review method with narrative techniques. According to Kosztyán, Csizmadiab, & Katona (2012), narrative reviews are aimed at identifying related phenomena through summarizing, selecting, and focusing on various literature related to phenomena of interest as evidence.

B. Analyzed Data Criteria

After collecting and selecting several journals from the various sources mentioned, a total of 25 journals were

selected according to the topics in this study with publication years ranging from 2013 to 2022 and having samples related to college students-employees. In the process of collecting literature, this research uses keywords, such as work-school conflict, work-study conflict, work-school interface, work-study interface, journal of work-study conflict, work-college conflict.

The journals selected for this study included Journal of Bussiness and Psychology, Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies, Journal of Organizational Behavior, The Journal of Psychology, Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Ekonomi Manajemen, Mix: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen, Dinasti International Journal of Management Science, Dinasti International Journal of Digital Business Management, Jurnal Empati, Journal of Career Development, Pensando Psicología, Psychology, Society, & Education, Journal of Psychology and Social Health, Jurnal Psikologi Integratif, Psychology Journal of Mental Health, Journal of Occupational Health Psychology, Community, Work & Family, Psychological Reports, Journal of Vocational Behavior, International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance, Journal of American College Health, e-Jurnal Apresiasi Ekonomi, dan AkMen Jurnal Ilmiah, American Psychologist, Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews, Psymphatic: Jurnal Ilmiah Psikologi.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Causes Factor Work-School Conflict

After collecting data and reviewing, the two roles can contribute causes factors in the work-school conflict experienced by college students-employees. This is probably because work-school conflict has the potential to become a two-way concept (Laughman, Boyd, & Rusbaan, 2016). In addition, college student-employees as individuals also contribute to the possibility of experiencing work-school conflict. The research results related to the causes factor in work-school conflict will be described in more detail in Table 1 below.

Table 1 Findings Selected from Literature Related to Causes Factor

Authors (Year)	Significant Findings
Andrade (2017) pp. 83-84	Working hours are said to have contributed to an increase in work-school conflict, therefore special attention is needed on the organization of work related to the work schedule, the type and context in which the work is carried out, to the characteristics of the task demands.
Andrade (2018) pp. 221	Psychological detachment from work has a negative relationship with work-school conflict, which explains situations where individuals no longer think about work-related matters outside of working hours can reduce the level of work-school conflict. In the context of psychological detachment from work, it is not just physically far from work, still, psychologically individuals must also be detached from all tasks related to work to avoid the vulnerability of multiple roles in the work-school conflict.
Creed, French & Hood (2015) pp. 52	Research has found that experiencing more work-based time demands and receiving fewer psychological rewards at work is associated with more work-school conflict. Psychological rewards are related to increased status and privileges that employees get in the domain at work which will help performance in other domains.
Creed, Hood & Hu (2020) pp. 341	Research finds that working hours are related to work-school conflict. Where working hours are included in one of the job characteristics measured, namely job demands.
Lederer, Autry, Day & Oswalt (2015)	Research has found that the time taken up for work (work hours) has an effect on working students which results in being overwhelmed and a lack of time to rest.

Authors (Year)	Significant Findings
pp. 404-405	
McNall & Michel (2016) pp. 12-14	School-specific core self-evaluations and perceived organizational support for school has a significant direct negative effect on work-school conflict. Where the support provided by the organization to working students enables them to experience more benefits and reduce the dual role conflict of work-school conflict.
Octavia & Nugraha (2013) pp. 49-50	Adversity quotient has a negative correlation with work-school conflict. This shows that if working students have high scores on the adversity quotient will experience low work-school conflict. This opinion emphasizes that students with a high adversity quotient will be stronger and able to face obstacles to carry out two roles at once, namely as students and as workers with high working hours.
Setyowati & Nurhayati (2019) pp. 109	The study found workload had a significant positive effect of 52.2% on work-school conflict, where the psychological stress load dimension played the biggest role in work-school conflict.
Ufaira & Pratiwi (2019) pp. 23-24	Locus of control is said to have a role in work-school conflict among working students. Whereas the whole, the locus of control variable makes an effective contribution to work-school conflict by 10.5%. If examined based on its aspects, internal locus of control has a negative effect on work-school conflict, while external locus of control has a positive effect on work-school conflict. This is because individuals who have higher internal control will be more confident in being able to control problems related to multiple roles in cases of work-school conflict. Meanwhile, if individuals place control on their externals (outside themselves), individuals tend to feel that all beliefs depend on the surrounding environment, so individuals were less able to control themselves regarding the dual roles in the case of work-school conflict.
Wan, Feng, Meng, Zhai, and Konopaske (2021) pp. 12-14	Work time pressure correlates positively with work-school conflict via work-school boundary permeability, where the boundary between how students handle or manage school-related tasks and responsibilities with their work is taken into account. Working students have two life roles, so the vulnerability to work-school conflict must be managed by controlling and limiting roles cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally when in two different situations.
Wyland, Lester, Mone, and Winkel (2013) pp. 349-350	School involvement physically has a significant positive effect on work-school conflict. Thus, while devoting more time and effort to school roles, it results in fewer resources (time and energy) for work roles. Thus, working students must be able to understand between workload and the amount of physical involvement in school.
Wyland, Lester, Ehrhardt, and Standifer (2015) pp. 191-192, 197-201	Job demands and school demands have a positive correlation with work-school conflict. This shows that high demands in one role (work or college) can cause pressure in other roles (work-school conflict). This is because the time and effort spent is more dominant in carrying out one role, will reduce the time and effort for the demands of other roles. In addition, work interpersonal support (supervisors and colleagues) has a negative correlation with work-school conflict. Interpersonal support, both from the college or work environment, felt by working students who are trying to balance their roles at work and in college will provide benefits for dividing responsibilities between college and work. Then, school control has a negative correlation with work-school conflict. School control related to commitment to school. School control is used to manage individual responsibilities related to roles in school. Working students who have the ability to manage class schedules and activities at school will reduce demanding situations related to roles at school and roles at work, so working students tend to experience fewer work-school conflicts.

A review of the literature found describes several factors that can cause work-school conflict in college student-employees. work-school conflict causes factors are then grouped into three parts based on the source, namely from the individual itself consisting of psychological detachment from work, adversity quotient, and locus of control. Then, the causes factors related to roles in school consist of school involvement, school demands, school control, and school-specific core self-evaluation. The last cause factor is related to roles in the workplace which consist of job demands, job resources, and psychological rewards. These factors are explained in more detail below.

➤ *Individual*

The first factor that leads to the emergence of work-school conflict in individuals is **Psychological Detachment from Work**, conditions in which individuals are able to completely detach themselves from work, not only physically but also psychologically. Psychological detachment from work occurs when individuals who have been outside work time completely discard thoughts related to their work. That is, individuals no longer carry busyness, assignments, and other workloads outside working hours (Sonntag & Krueger, 2006; Andrade, 2018). The case of work-school conflict experienced by student-college employees more or less illustrates how students who work are less able to divide between the roles of students and employees. Often students bring school assignments into their work, and vice versa. So

that the relationship created between psychological detachment from work and work-school conflict produces a negative correlation. This is evidenced by research conducted by Andrade (2018) that when individuals have the awareness to completely detach from workload before individuals switch to other professional roles, the vulnerability to multiple roles in work-school conflict cases will decrease. Because individuals can share their respective role responsibilities according to the situation where individuals are with the minimal workload they carry.

Adversity Quotient, is a person's ability to face and respond to difficulties that exist in life, such as stress and various obstacles experienced. Adversity quotient can help individuals see challenges as opportunities for career development, strengthen individual abilities, and focus on dreams regardless of what happens (Stoltz, 2005; Huda & Mulyana, 2018; Wolor, 2020). Stoltz (2005) adds the characteristics of individuals with higher adversity quotient, having greater persistence, creativity, endurance, health, productivity, and performance than individuals with low adversity quotient. Adversity quotient is also able to predict how individuals respond to various changes. Because of this, in the case of work-school conflict experienced by college student-employees who are currently dividing their roles as students and employees, if they have a high adversity quotient, it is certain that college student-employees will succeed in passing obstacles related to multiple roles. It was proven through research conducted by Octavia & Nugraha (2013), that adversity quotient has a negative correlation with work-school conflict. Where college student-employees with high adversity quotient can be stronger in facing multiple roles, even with high working hours, their performance has exceeded performance expectations. The low level of work-school conflict is known because individuals have control as an aspect of the adversity quotient that contributes in guiding individuals to adapt their roles to changes in the two situations.

Locus of Control, in general, is explained by Rotter (1990) regarding how individual expectations of reinforcement are controlled by oneself or the outside environment. In more detail, Rotter (1990) divides locus of control into two aspects. Individuals with an internal locus of control emphasize that the expectations of an outcome or reinforcement related to their behavior depend entirely on personal characteristics, meaning that individuals independently control reinforcement. Meanwhile, individuals with an external locus of control have hope that the results or reinforcement depend entirely on situational circumstances, meaning that individuals rely on luck, fate, or even other people in controlling reinforcement. Research conducted by Ufaira and Pratiwi (2019) found the results of locus of control had an effect on work-school conflict, where internal locus of control had a negative effect, and external locus of control had a positive effect. Crider (1983) said that individuals with an internal locus of control are characterized as hard workers, have high initiative, are able to solve problems, have the perception that individuals have to try if they want to be successful, and think effectively. Meanwhile, individuals with an external locus of control have less initiative, have the

perception that external factors will control the results so that individuals give up easily, seek less information, and are easily influenced by others. Because of the above, when individuals (in this case college student-employees) face multiple roles in cases of work-school conflict, individuals with high internal locus of control are better able to control their roles and place them according to the situation, between being a student and employees. Thus, individuals who have an external locus of control will have more difficulty controlling themselves because individuals relies on the outside environment, which is not necessarily a factor outside of themselves that can support their current situation to manage multiple roles in the case of work-school conflict.

➤ *Roles in School*

School involvement physically, refers to how individuals give time and effort to the role of the school (Wyland, Lester, Mone, & Winkel, 2013). Meanwhile, **school demand** is a condition that has been determined in the program at school, where every student is expected to be involved in these predetermined requirements (Brenner, Hofmann, & Weddington, 1964). Schools, be it universities or colleges, are one of the main places where humans play a role in life (Super, 1980). So, school is a place where humans carry out the role of a student. Super (1980) said that humans carry out many roles in life. In college student-employee, the individual is carrying out a dual role, namely as a college student and employee. However, Marks (1977) states that humans basically have limited resources (such as time, energy, and attention), using resources in one role, will reduce resources for other roles. Thus, in college student-employees, the role as a high college student at school will allow disruption of the role as an employee at work (work-school conflict). This was further demonstrated by research conducted by Wyland, Lester, Mone, and Winkel (2013) that school involvement physically has a significant positive effect on work-school conflict. Mills, Lingard, & Wakefield (2007) also revealed that work-school conflict occurs when involvement in one role interferes with other roles. In addition, Wyland, Lester, Ehrhardt, and Standifer (2015) through research, also revealed that high school demands will cause pressure on the role of an employee, this is because one role uses more dominant time and effort in carrying out the demands of one role, will reduce the time and effort for the demands of other roles.

School control in this study is more related to when students' commitment to school is used to manage responsibilities related to their role in school (Wyland, Lester, Ehrhardt, & Standifer, 2015). Control is related to doing what the individual knows is best for the long term and immediately profitable, when faced with a choice (Duckworth, Gendler, & Gross, 2014). So, for students who work, school control is quite necessary to regulate their roles in school, so that working students can balance the responsibilities of the two roles they play. This is also in line with research conducted by Wyland, Lester, Ehrhardt, and Standifer (2015) that school control has a negative correlation with work-school conflict, which indicates that when working students have high school control, they tend to experience low work-school conflict. Furthermore, Wyland, Lester, Ehrhardt,

and Standifer (2015) stated that working students who have the ability to manage class schedules and their activities at school, this will reduce demanding situations related to roles at school and at work.

School-Specific Core Self-Evaluation, refers to how individuals assess themselves regarding their eligibility, abilities and competencies. Core self-evaluation is said to be a variable that can describe the orientation of personality traits or individual characteristics, and how individuals relate to their environment (Judge, Bono, Erez, & Locke, 2005; Judge & Hurst, 2007). McNall & Michel (2016) stated that core self-evaluation plays an important role in managing individual roles in the context of work, family, and the work-school interface. Which the focus here emphasizes more on the specifications of the school. Therefore, it is very important to apply self-evaluation to college-student employees who are currently facing dual roles as both students and employees. It is said that self-evaluation can help individuals better manage each role. Research conducted by McNall & Michel (2016) shows that school-specific core self-evaluation has a significant direct negative effect on work-school conflict. Core self-evaluation allows individuals to choose the most effective coping strategies in dealing with the pressures of demanding school-work assignments. And thus, the individual's stress level will be lower, so that individual is better able to separate work and school matters, and solve various conflicts more optimally (Mueller, Judge, & Scott, 2009).

➤ *Roles in the Workplace*

Job Demands are described as physical, social, or organizational aspects that demand effort from individuals either physically or mentally (Demerouti, Bakker, Nachreiner, & Schaufeli, 2001). Demands in the workplace are known to be directly related to student-employee work-school conflict, which must balance the roles of both students and employees. Wyland, Lester, Ehrhardt, and Standifer 's research. (2015) found that job demands are positively related to work-school conflict, meaning that high job demands have an impact on high work-school conflict. will spend his time and energy in an effort to meet the demands of work. Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) explained that there are 2 types of job demands, namely quantitative demands, for example workload, and qualitative demands, for example emotional. The literature review here found that quantitative demands are related to work-school conflict, namely workload and working time.

First, related to **workload** which refers to the amount of work that must be done by employees within a certain time frame (Green, Cox, Lewis, Silber, Willerton, 2016). During work, work overload can occur for employees when job demands exceed the employee's ability to handle them (Senbagam, 2021). The workload itself can affect many aspects of employees related to work such as work stress and employee performance (Cahyaningtyas & Santosa, 2021), and also affects the individual which, in this review, influences work-school conflict. Research by Setyowati and Nurhayati (2019) found that workload had a positive effect of 52.2% on work-school conflict, meaning that the higher the workload, the higher the work-school conflict in college student-

employees. Furthermore, it was found that the psychological stress load dimension has the greatest influence on work-school conflict. Reid and Nygren (1988) explain psychological stress load as anything that contributes to individual confusion, frustration, and/or anxiety, where stressors can come from fear of failure, tension, unfamiliarity, or disorientation. This psychological stressor can then trigger the emergence of work-school conflict in individuals because when individuals feel afraid they will fail in carrying out work assignments that are accompanied by assignments at school it leads to anxiety, this illustrates how conflict ultimately occurs due to workload borne by the individual.

Second, **working time**, which in this review is related to **working hours, work-based time demands, and working time pressure** which were all found to be associated with work-school conflict in college student-employees. Working hours, in a more general context, are explained as a certain amount of time employees spend at work in a day (Cambridge Dictionary, 2022). For employees who have multiple roles, namely working and studying, subjectively the demands on working hours can be seen as a burden. This happens because the limited time for work results in the availability of time to do activities and other tasks. Confirming this, a number of studies have found that working hours have an effect on work-school conflict (Andrade, 2017; Creed, Hood & Hu, 2020; Lederer, Autry, Day & Oswalt, 2015). Furthermore, work-based time demands and working time pressure see time in a more specific context for certain jobs. Work-based time demands lead to the amount of time needed for certain jobs, Creed, French, and Hood's (2015) study found that when individuals feel work demands a lot of time it will result in disruption of their schoolwork, this illustrates how work-based time demands related to work-school conflict in employees who have multiple roles. Then, working time pressure refers to the amount of work that must be completed within the allotted time, where the individual will be stressed because the work is felt to be too much compared to the time available to complete it (Sonntag, Pundt, & Albrecht, 2014). In this case, time is limited because college student-employees carry out roles at work and school so that they have workloads from both. Wan, Feng, Meng, Zhai, and Konopaske's (2021) research, found that working time pressure is positively correlated with work-school conflict through work-school boundary permeability, where the boundary separates the tasks of individuals who have two roles, so it is important for working students to build their own boundaries so that conflicts between roles may occur. can be managed both cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally according to where working students are and what tasks must be done at that time.

Job resources are described by Demerouti, Bakker, Nachreiner and Schaufeli (2001) as any physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspect of work that helps employees achieve their work goals, reduces job demands as well as their physiological and psychological costs, and encourages growth and self-development employee. One of the resources in the workplace that can be useful for employees is obtaining social support. In the American Psychological Association Dictionary (2015) social

support is described as assistance to other individuals that is done to help them cope with stressors. In this literature review it was found that work interpersonal support and perceived organizational support can help employees who have multiple roles in overcoming conflict. Work interpersonal support, meaning that individuals get help or encouragement from other people in their work environment. Cooper and Kahn (2013) explain that support can come from the workplace, such as superiors, supervisors and colleagues. Research has found that work interpersonal support that comes from supervisors and coworkers has a negative correlation with work-school conflict, so large support can help individuals share their responsibilities so that conflict due to work and school roles can be reduced (Wyland, Lester, Ehrhardt, & Standifer, 2015). Perceived support can also come from the organization, namely perceived organizational support. Perceived organizational support (POS) is explained as the extent to which employees believe that the organization values their contributions and cares about their welfare (Robbins & Judge, 2018). McNall and Michel's research (2016) found that perceived organizational support for school has a direct effect on work-school conflict. The organizational support felt by college student-employees regarding their education can help student-employees manage their roles both at school and at work thereby reducing work-school conflict.

Psychological rewards at work are intended to provide stimulating incentives, as well as a form of appreciation to employees for achievements at work (De Gieter, De Cooman, Pepermans, & Jegers, 2010). According to Voydanoff (2004) that these psychological rewards will provide feelings of

worth and value to employees, and can be used in carrying out multiple roles that cause tension, by releasing psychologically through positive emotions and energy. Apart from that, psychological rewards are also related to increased status and privileges that employees get in the domain at work which will help performance in other domains (Creed, French, & Hood, 2015). That is, students who work when they get psychological rewards at work will give them a feeling of worth and value, which will later release positive emotions and energy that can be used in facilitating role responsibilities at work and at school. Creed, French, & Hood (2015) in the results of research conducted, shows that a few psychological rewards received at work will be associated with more work-school conflict.

B. *Impact Work-School Conflict at Work and Health*

After collecting and reviewing data, work-school conflict does not only have an impact on roles at school, but can also have an impact on roles at work. Mills, Lingard, and Wakefield (2007) also stated that work-school conflict is a phenomenon involving two roles, where responsibility for the role of an employee will interfere with responsibility for the role of a student, conversely responsibility for the role of a student can interfere with the responsibility of the student responsibility for the role of employee. It was also found in the selected journals used in this study, that work-school conflict can also have an impact on roles at work. In addition, it was also found that work-school conflict can also affect individual health. All findings will be described in detail in Table 2.

Table 2 Findings Selected from Literature Related to Impact at Work and Health

Authors (Year)	Significant Findings
Amri and Putra (2018) pp. 143-144	Work-school conflict has a significant positive effect on fatigue. That is, the higher the work-school conflict, the higher the fatigue experienced by working students. In addition, work-school conflict also has a significant positive effect on poor sleep quality. This shows that the higher the work-school conflict, the worse the quality of sleep experienced by working students.
Fadhilah and Nurtjahjanti (2018) pp. 129-130	Work-school conflict has a significant negative correlation with job satisfaction among working students, with an effect of 17%.
Kurniawan, Jufri, Gunawan, Yani, and Priyono (2021) pp. 306	Research finds work-school conflict has an effect on burnout
Laughman, Boyd, and Rusbasan (2016) pp. 418-420	Work-school conflict has a negative correlation with job satisfaction. In addition, work-school conflict has a positive relationship with turnover intentions. Work-school conflict also has a positive correlation with burnout. When working students experience high work-school conflict, they will also have low job satisfaction, high turnover intentions, and high burnout. This is because working students experience stress due to drained resources to be present in both roles, namely work and school responsibilities.
Lubis and Nurhayati, (2020) pp. 289 & 292	There is a significant effect of work-school conflict of 18.1% on job satisfaction. In this case, strain based conflict is the dimension that most influences job satisfaction.
Lederer, Autry, Day and Oswalt (2015) pp. 404-405	Research has found that working students feel they have fewer rest days than students who don't work. Then students who work are more likely to feel overwhelmed in the last 30 days compared to students who are not working.
McNall and Michel (2016) pp. 12-14	Work-school conflict has a significant direct effect on psychological health. Working students certainly experience fatigue while at school, coupled with work demands which involve the second role of students as employees in the office which will have a negative impact on declining health.
Nastasia, Sari, and Candra (2022)	Research has found a significant negative relationship between work-school conflict and entrepreneurial satisfaction, where the higher the work-school conflict, the lower the

Authors (Year)	Significant Findings
pp. 255	entrepreneurial satisfaction, and vice versa. Work-school conflict makes an effective contribution of 34% to entrepreneurial satisfaction
Nurfitria and Masykur (2016) pp. 768	Research has found that there is a negative relationship between work-school conflict and work engagement, meaning that the higher the work-school conflict, the lower the work engagement. It was also found that work-school conflict had an effect on work engagement of 39.2%.
Nurhayati, Saputra, Santosa, Rahmani, and Ariyanto (2022) pp. 243	Work-school conflict has a negative effect on employee performance. The division of work roles that cause stress, as well as the tight schedule of activities, will interfere with performance, both at work and at school.
Oviatt, Baumann, Bennett, and Garza (2017) pp. 436-437, 443-444	Work-school conflict separately has a positive correlation with consuming alcohol, marijuana, smoking, and depressive symptoms. In addition, work-school conflict has a negative correlation with physical health. With the effects given by cannabis, individuals who experience high work-school conflict can relax after a hard day at work, but can also try to understand complex topics. Cigarettes which have a calming effect, will also facilitate like marijuana, can relax without reducing performance. Work-school conflict causes internal conditions to be unpleasant, and the use of these substances to overcome these conditions. This also shows that work-school conflict is related to psychological tension.
Park and Sprung (2013) pp. 388, 390-391	Work-school conflict has a negative relationship with the psychological health of working students. Experience related to demands to fulfill both school and work responsibilities increases psychological tension in students which in turn causes excessive worry, triggers stress and anxiety. This work-school conflict will be considered as a barrier stressor rather than a challenge for individuals who do not have high personal fulfillment, such as considering work as fun, work is to achieve new experiences, and so on. Likewise in the lack of fulfillment of work-school facilitation and lack of support from superiors or colleagues.
Park and Sprung (2015) pp. 114-119	Work-school conflict has a negative relationship with sleep quality. That is, when employees experience high work-school conflict, employees will experience poor sleep quality. In addition, work-school conflict also has a positive relationship with fatigue. This shows that when employees experience high work-school conflict, employees will also experience high fatigue. This is because work-school conflict drains resources, where human resources are basically limited. Ignoring one domain for another domain will have a negative impact on the neglected domain, so that working students tend to force themselves to use resources that have an impact on fatigue.
Wyland, Lester, Mone, and Winkel (2013) pp. 352-355	Work-school conflict has a negative effect on the three dimensions of job performance, namely job dedication, interpersonal facilitation (such as not being supportive, fair, and helping colleagues), and task performance. Employee performance can be distracted when they are busy and "scattered". When working students experience increasing difficulties in managing time and effort hence causing performance degradation.
Wyland, Lester, Ehrhardt, and Standifer (2015) pp. 197-201	Work-school conflict has a negative correlation with task performance. Supervisors tend to feel the quality of work is declining because working students have difficulty balancing school and work.
Yahya and Yulianto (2018) pp. 569	Work-school conflict has a positive effect on the stress of working students by 33.7%, so in this case the conflict that occurs can increase stress. It was also found that work-school conflict had a significant positive effect on student burnout by 30.3%.
Yusri (2021) pp. 12-14	Work-school conflict acts as a significant predictor of the life satisfaction of working students, with a negative correlation showing that when working students experience an increase in work-school conflict, their life satisfaction will decrease. Where later it can interfere with psychological health such as contributing to fatigue and stress due to multiple roles.

The above literature review illustrates the impact caused by work-school conflict both for the individuals and for the company where the employee works. The impact of work-school conflict is then grouped into two parts, namely the impact on companies consists of job satisfaction, burnout, turnover intention, work engagement, employee performance, and job performance. Then the impact of work-school conflict on individual health which consists of physical health, psychological health, and life satisfaction. The impact of each work-school conflict is explained in more detail below.

➤ At Work

Job satisfaction, defined by Aydıntan & Koç (2016) is an individual's affectively positive response to how the overall work situation is. Job satisfaction for each individual is not the same, depending on job characteristics, sense of responsibility, education, and past experiences that accompany and provide intrinsic results (Fadhilah & Nurtjahjanti, 2018). Some individuals show satisfaction in their work through a sense of satisfaction in entrepreneurship. **Entrepreneurial satisfaction** is expressed as the attitudes and feelings shown by an entrepreneur when enjoys the achievements of entrepreneurship (Fatkhurahman, 2016). Job

satisfaction can also be achieved through several factors, such as physical, social, financial, and psychological. Where psychological factors are related to individual skills (Fadhilah & Nurtjahjanti, 2018). It is known that currently many of the employees who work also hold the status of students. In this case, we call it a college student-employee. And it is not uncommon to find cases of work-school conflict in college student-employees due to a lack of psychological skills in positioning themselves in the roles they play in college or at work. When college student-employee act as students, they will contribute more to lecture activities than work, of course, this affects a decrease in work performance (Wyland, Lester, Mone, & Winkel, 2013). This is proven through several studies which show that indeed work-school conflict has a negative and significant correlation to job satisfaction and entrepreneurship satisfaction. So that in the end, it can reach a decline in health (Laughman, Boyd, & Rusbasan, 2016); Fadhilah & Nurtjahjanti, 2018; Lubis, & Nurhayati, 2020; Nastasia, Sari, & Candra, 2022). Therefore, in the case of work-school conflict, it is important to optimally manage individual psychological factors when trying to describe the division of roles in carrying out responsibilities both as students and employees.

Burnout, is a form of combination of severe exhaustion, negative and cynical behavior related to work (Demerouti, Bakker, Nachreiner, & Schaufeli, 2021). Burnout can be characterized by low levels of energy and poor identification with a job (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2010). Too much work (Rigio, 2013) can cause burnout. In addition, according to Maslach and Leiter (2016) work overload can also cause burnout, because you will have little to rest and restore balance so that it drains the capacity of employees to meet job demands. Meanwhile, the student-employee college is not only responsible for fulfilling the demands of the role as an employee, but also the demands of the role as a student, so this will reduce the capacity of the student-employee college to meet the demands of work. This is shown by the results of several studies which state that work-school conflict is related to burnout, where the higher the work-school conflict, the higher the burnout that will be experienced (Laughman, Boyd, & Rusbasan, 2016; Yahya & Yulianto, 2018).

Turnover intention, is a situation where employees decide to leave the organization, either on a voluntary or coercive basis. One of the things that causes turnover intention in employees is the tension they feel when facing role conflict. (Lazzari, Alvarez, & Ruggieri, 2022). Conflict between roles itself is considered a stressor which is correlated with increasing turnover intention (Laughman, Boyd, & Rusbasan, 2016). We all know that the conflict crisis currently being faced by college student-employees regarding the current situation is the dual roles of students and employees. And if the placement of work-school conflict here is a burdensome stressor, then college student-employees tend to perceive that they will not be able to fulfill their responsibilities in their various roles professionally (Brunel & Grima, 2010). As for how the relationship between work-school conflict and turnover intention has been discussed through research conducted by Laughman, Boyd, & Rusbasan (2016), with the result that there is an increase in turnover

intention caused by high work-school conflict as a stress-triggering variable that depletes individual resources through multiple roles.

Work engagement expressed by Schaufeli, Salanove, Romá, and Bakker (2002), namely a state of mind that is positive, and satisfying related to work characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. Vigor refers to high energy and mental resilience when working. Dedication refers to a high sense of significance, enthusiasm, inspiration, pride and challenges when working. Meanwhile, absorption is related to full concentration and deeply engrossed in a job, so that time seems to go fast and employees feel reluctant to stop doing that work. Thus, employees who have work engagement tend not to feel tired when working hard because they think work is fun, but they are not addicted to work (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008). Employees who have high work engagement are also characterized by being more productive, creative, and willing to work harder. In college student-employees, the multiple roles that are carried out will drain energy, so college student-employees tend to reduce work engagement (Spreitzer, Lam, & Fritz, 2010). This was also expressed by Nurfitriah and Masykur (2016) in a study conducted that work-school conflict has a negative relationship with work engagement, and has an effect of 39.2%. So, the higher the work-school conflict, the lower the work engagement.

Job performance, described as the achievement or completion of an employee's work assignments which also describes how the task was accomplished (Magableh, Omar, & Al-Tarawneh, 2021). Job performance is very important for the organization because it is related to the success or failure of the organization in achieving goals (Rigio, 2013). For working students, conflict due to multiple roles can affect performance. Research Nurhayati, Saputra, Santosa, Rahmani, and Ariyanto (2022). found that high work-school conflict resulted in low performance for employees due to their work roles and busy schedules. Wyland, Lester, Mone, and Winkel (2013) also said that work-school conflict has a negative effect on job performance, including each of the job performance dimensions, namely job dedication, interpersonal facilitation, and task performance. Job performance, explained Motowidlo, Borman, and Schmit (1997) consists of two forms, namely task performance and contextual performance. Task performance is related to the technical core of the organization, such as process implementation, maintenance and technical service. Meanwhile, contextual performance is related to how to maintain the organizational, social, and psychological environment. Contextual performance is then divided into two aspects, namely (1) interpersonal facilitation, which is related to cooperative behavior, considerate, and helps to improve the performance of colleagues; and (2) job dedication which is related to self-discipline, motivation, hard work, initiative, and following rules to support success in achieving organizational goals (Van Scotter & Motowidlo, 1996). According to Wyland, Lester, Mone, and Winkel (2013), working students who experience work-school conflict can lead to poor job performance, this is because working students are busy and must be divided in fulfilling role responsibilities at work and at school. So, when working

students have difficulty managing time and effort, it will cause a decrease in performance. This will also cause Supervisors to tend to value the quality of work decreasing (Wyland, Lester, Ehrhardt, & Standifer, 2015). Thus, conflict management skills are important for working students to fulfill their responsibilities optimally through quality performance.

➤ *Individual Health*

Physical health, is when an individual is able to carry out an activity, even one that is quite strenuous and/or for quite a long time, without experiencing significant fatigue or having remaining energy reserves, and with these remaining energy reserves, the individual is still able to perform other activities, enjoying free time, or unexpected emergency events (Irwansyah, 2006; Nenggala, 2006). Based on this definition, every human being should have physical health to be able to carry out activities optimally with optimal body condition. This should also be owned by working students to be able to carry out both roles optimally, but when working students experience work-school conflict it will have an impact on physical health. Oviatt, Baumann, Bennett, and Garza (2017) in their research also stated that work-school conflict has a negative correlation with physical health, meaning that working students who experience work-school conflict will have a negative impact on physical health. Oviatt, Baumann, Bennett, and Garza (2017) in his research also stated that work-school conflict separately had a positive correlation with the consumption of alcohol, marijuana and cigarettes. This is because these three things can have a relaxing effect after going through a difficult working day, but can understand complex topics, so working students who experience work-school conflict can relax without reducing performance.

In addition, research conducted by Park and Sprung (2015) found that work-school conflict has a negative relationship with sleep quality and a positive relationship with fatigue. The results of this study are also in line with research conducted by Amri and Putra (2018). Students who work mean that they have multiple roles, there is an obligation to complete the demands and responsibilities of roles at school and at work. Humans have limited resources (such as time, energy, and attention) (Marks, 1997), but ignoring one domain for another will have a negative impact on the neglected domain, so that working students tend to force themselves to use resources that have an impact on fatigue (Park & Sprung, 2015).

Psychological health is described by World Health Organization (2022) as a state of well-being that helps individuals cope with stress, realize their abilities, and be able to properly carry out study and work activities. Thus, good psychology is important so that individuals can function optimally in all their activities. Psychological health can be disrupted due to conflict (World Health Organization, 2008). For students who work, conflict can occur when they are faced with conflicting demands for responsibility. In line with this, research has found that work-school conflict has an effect on individual psychological health where poor health is caused by high conflict between roles (McNall & Michel, 2016; Park & Sprung, 2013; Yusri, 2021). Poor psychological

health due to conflict, in this literature is described by symptoms of depression, stress, and feelings of being overwhelmed. Research Oviatt, Baumann, Bennett, and Garza (2017) found work-school conflict correlated with depressive symptoms, where high conflict led to high depressive symptoms that appeared in individuals. Depression is a negative affective state indicated by extreme unhappiness, dissatisfaction, feelings of sadness, pessimism, and hopelessness, which can interfere with individuals living life (American Psychological Association Dictionary, 2015). Then, the emergence of stress in individuals, research has found that high work-school conflict also triggers high stress (Park & Sprung, 2013; Yahya & Yulianto, 2018; Yusri, 2021). Working students are also prone to feeling overwhelmed, research by Lederer, Autry, Day and Oswald (2015) found that being overwhelmed tends to occur in students who are working compared to those who are not working. So this illustrates how college student-employees in their efforts to fulfill responsibilities on two sides can cause feelings of being overwhelmed.

Life Satisfaction, is an individual cognitive evaluation in several domains related to how feelings/emotions, desires, and expectations depend heavily on social comparisons (Aydintan & Koç, 2016; Unanue, Gómez, Cortez, Oyanedel, Mendiburo-Seguel, 2017). Life satisfaction can cover individual life in the fields of education and work. Where in the field of education, life satisfaction can affect individual academic potential. Meanwhile, in the context of work, life satisfaction is often associated with employee job satisfaction. In the case of college student-employees who are facing dual roles as students and employees, it is important for college student-employees to have life satisfaction in order to balance their roles in controlling academic commitment and quality of work life, so that they will be far from work-school conflict (Aydintan & Koç, 2016; Yusri, 2021). It is known that the discussion of work-school conflict cases has generated a lot of interest, one of which is how this work-school conflict can affect individual life satisfaction. Based on research conducted by Yusri (2021), the results showed that there was a negative correlation between work-school conflict and life satisfaction, meaning that individuals who have increased work-school conflict will experience a significant decrease in their life satisfaction. What will happen when life satisfaction is low is that individuals are more susceptible to feeling tired and stressed due to being overwhelmed by multiple roles. Where actually life satisfaction has a fairly high contribution in managing work and school demands. If individuals are more satisfied and enjoy the flow of life, then individuals will be more able to play a role in every situation they are running.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The development of the times has made the quality of human resources a fairly important value in corporate competition, as well as for employees as individuals in career development and competition in the job market. It is not uncommon for students to take on the role of employees in an effort to prepare and improve their quality according to the company's current needs. However, it is not only a positive impact that is offered to students who also work, but in fact it

can have a negative impact, if it cannot balance the responsibilities of the role as a student with the responsibilities of the role as a worker. Considering according to Marks (1977) that humans basically have limited resources (such as time, energy, and attention), so using resources in one role, will reduce resources in other roles. This is known as work-school conflict, where responsibility in one role interferes with responsibility in another role.

So far, the impact of work-school conflict has been linked more to roles in school, but work-school conflict can potentially be a two-way concept (Laughman, Boyd, & Rusabasan, 2016), so that the impact on roles in the workplace also needs to be considered to produce quality and competitive human resources. Thus, this study aims to discuss the causes factors, as well as the impact at work and health in work-school conflict in college student-employees. In this study, 25 selected and reviewed journals were used. Journals are selected based on established criteria, in accordance with the research objectives. After collecting and reviewing, it was found that the causes factors related to work-school conflict in college student-employees were grouped into three, namely those originating from individuals, related to roles in school, and related to roles in the workplace. Meanwhile, the impact of work-school conflict is grouped into two, namely the workplace and individual health.

The causes factors originating from individuals consist of psychological detachment from work, adversity quotient, and locus of control. Causes factors originating from roles related to school, consisting of physical school involvement, school demand, school control, and school-specific core self-evaluation. Meanwhile, the causes factor comes from roles related to the workplace, namely job demands, job resources, and psychological rewards at work. On the other hand, the impact at work on college student-employees who experience work-school conflict, namely job satisfaction, turnover intention, work engagement, and job performance. Work-school conflict also has an impact on the health of college students-employees, namely related to physical health, mental health, and life satisfaction.

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted, the researchers suggest to college student-employees who have responsibilities at work and school to develop effective coping strategies when carrying out their roles as students and employees. One of the coping strategies that can be applied is adaptive coping techniques to manage stress by getting used to a healthy lifestyle, meditation, relaxation, and exercise. The importance of preparing schedules and good time management will help college student-employees know the priority of tasks so that there is no overlapping in fulfilling the responsibilities of the two roles. The application of psychological detachment from work is an effort that needs to be considered in preventing work-school conflict, in this case it is recommended that college student-employees make the most of their free time to rest.

This also requires companies that have college student-employees to be involved in avoiding the possibility of work-school conflict by giving college student-employees time off every week, and not contacting them outside of work time, in order to provide opportunities to rest so that college student-employees can recharge their energy. In addition, companies can provide support by building a supportive environment, so that college student-employees do not feel burdened at work which can lead to work-school conflict. Based on the results of this study as well, future researchers are expected to explore more related to the causes of the individual's own factors and the impact of work-school conflict in the workplace, so that scientific discussion related to work-school conflict can be more extensive.

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